

Apparatus : A Beckman model DU-2 spectrophotometer, with 10 mm quartz cells, an ELICO pH-meter, model LI-10T with saturated calomel and glass electrodes and a Ganson flask shaker with to and fro action were used in the present studies.

General procedure : To an aliquot of solution containing 58.9 μg cobalt, enough acetic acid (0.2 M) and sodium acetate (0.2 M) are added to get pH 6.0 to 7.2 in 25 ml volume. The solution is shaken with 10 ml of 0.001 M HMMCO in benzene for 15 min. The organic layer is separated and its absorption is measured at 390 nm against reagent solution as a blank. The extracted cobalt is computed from calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra : The absorption spectra of the cobalt complex in benzene show a maximum at 390 nm. The molar absorptivity of the complex at 390 nm is 2.28×10^4 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The sensitivity of the method as defined by Sandell is 0.0026 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ at 390 nm. The system obeys Beer's law over the range of 0.6-17.7 μg cobalt per ml of benzene. The complex is stable up to 24 hr.

Effect of pH and HMMCO concentration : It is observed that the extraction is quantitative in the pH range 6.0-7.2. Below pH 6.0 extraction is incomplete and above pH 7.2 it decreases. There is no extraction below pH 3.0 and above pH 9.5. 10 ml of 0.001 M HMMCO in benzene at pH 6.5 suffice for quantitative extraction of cobalt.

Effect of solvent : To have a proper choice of non-aqueous solvent for the extraction of cobalt(II) from aqueous phase, several solvents like benzene, toluene, *p*-xylene, hexane, cyclohexane, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, *iso*-amyl alcohol, *n*-butanol, *iso*-butanol, cyclohexanol, *iso*-butylmethylketone, cyclohexanone, etc. were tried. It is revealed that benzene is the most suitable solvent for the present system. It is further noted that the extraction is quantitative in 10-15 min of agitation; a time of 15 min is therefore recommended.

Effect of diverse ions : Various ions were tested for possible interferences. The tolerance limit is set at the amount of foreign ion required to cause $\pm 2\%$ error in the recovery of cobalt. Ions such as alkali and alkaline earth metals, beryllium, aluminium, selenite, arsenite, halide anions, sulphite, thiosulphate, nitrate, nitrite are tolerated in the ratio of 1 : 200. Silver, cadmium, zinc, mercury, manganese, chromium, ruthenium, rhodium, gold, platinum and osmium(VIII) can be tolerated in twenty fold excess. Two fold excess of nickel does not interfere, while copper, palladium, iron(III), uranyl, vanadyl, thorium and EDTA interfere seriously.

Precision : The average absorbance found for 58.9 μg of cobalt is 0.230 ± 0.005 for 20 determinations. The relative standard deviation is $\pm 1.1\%$.

The method proposed here is simple, rapid, sensitive and applicable at trace concentration of cobalt. It is possible to separate and determine cobalt from various ions.

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Spectrophotometric Studies on Palladium(II) with 2-Thiopyrogallol and β -Mercapto-resorcylic Acid

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SULPHUR bearing ligands are long being used for photometric determination of palladium. Some of the most important ligands are dithio-oxamide¹, N, N'-bis-(3-dimethyl-aminopropyl) dithio-oxamide², 3-phenyl-3H-5-mercapto-1,3,4-thiadiazole-2-thion³, diethyldithiophosphate⁴, α -ethyl thio-isonicotinamide⁵ and 2-mercaptopyridine-1-oxide⁶.

In the present investigation attempts have been made to find some new chromogenic reagents for palladium with sulphur as donor atom. Effects on sensitivity with change of functional groups were also investigated. The stepwise formation constants k_1 and k_2 of the complexes PdL₁⁺ and PdL₂, respectively have been evaluated following the graphical extrapolation methods of Leden⁷ and Yatsimirskii⁸⁻¹⁰. The overall formation constants of the palladium complexes have also been evaluated by Harvey-Manning method¹¹.

Experimental

Equipment : A Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer and a Spektromom 204 with 1 cm quartz cells

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF Pd²⁺ COMPLEXES AT 27 ± 2°

Reagent	Leden's method			Yatsimirskii's method			Harvey-Manning's method
	log k ₁	log k ₂	log β ₂	log k ₁	log k ₂	log β ₂	log β ₂
I	4.41	4.03	8.44	4.42	4.07	8.49	10.58
II	3.87	3.67	7.54	4.27	3.76	7.88	8.60

were used for measurement of absorbance and for recording absorption spectra.

Synthesis of reagents : The reagent 2-thiopyrogallol (reagent I) was prepared by following the method of Pantlitschke and Benger¹² from 17.6 g resorcinol, 50 g copper sulphate and 31 g ammonium thiocyanate. The compound thus formed was filtered and neutralised with Na₂CO₃ followed by hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid. Thus 4-hydroxy-1,3(2H)-benzoxathiol-2-one (I), m.p. 160° was obtained. The reagent 2-thiopyrogallol was prepared *in situ* by dissolving (I) in 0.1 M sodium hydroxide and neutralising with acetic acid. (Analysis, Found : C, 50.55 ; H, 4.20 ; O, 22.46 ; S, 22.48. Calcd. for C₆H₆O₂S ; C, 50.70 ; H, 4.22 ; O, 22.53 ; S, 22.53%).

The reagent β-mercapto-resorcylic acid (reagent II) was prepared by dissolving β-resorcylic acid (7.7 g) in equivalent amount of sodium hydroxide solution. 25 g copper sulphate in 125 ml water was then added into the solution. The solution was cooled and treated with 20 g potassium thiocyanate in 25 ml water with vigorous stirring. The compound 4-hydroxy-1,3(2H) benzoxathiol-2-one-5-carboxylic acid was precipitated and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 260° with decomposition. (Analysis, Found : C, 49.20 ; H, 3.50 ; O, 27.95, S, 18.70%. Calcd. for C₇H₆O₅S ; C, 49.41 ; H, 3.53 ; O, 28.23 ; S, 18.82%).

Preparation of solutions : A standard solution of Pd²⁺ was prepared by dissolving 1 g ampule of PdCl₂ (Johnson Matthey) in 1 M hydrochloric acid and standardised by estimation as dimethylglyoximate¹³.

Freshly prepared 0.1% solutions of reagents I and II were used for the spectrophotometric studies.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra : The absorption spectra of 3.75 × 10⁻⁵ M Pd²⁺ with reagents I and II were worked out at pH 5.0 in 60 : 40 ethanol : water medium. It was found that both the complexes have λ_{max} at 430 nm.

Effect of pH and reagent concentrations : The complex with reagent I shows constant absorbance from pH 4.0 to 6.5 and with reagent II from pH 5.0 to 10.0. The optimum reagent concentration where the absorbance remains constant is from 3.0 to 8.0 ml of reagent I and 2.0 to 6.0 ml of reagent II.

Beer's law, optimum range, sensitivity and photometric error : The colour systems were found to obey Beer's law from 0.5 to 6 ppm of palladium with reagent I or II. The Ringbom¹⁴ plots showed that the optimum range is from 2-6 ppm for both the reagents. The percent relative error¹⁵ in this range was 2.77 and 2.73, respectively.

The molar absorptivity was found to be 9.60 × 10³ l.mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ and 1.10 × 10⁴ l.mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The sensitivity according to Sandell's definition was 0.011 and 0.010 μg cm⁻² of Pd²⁺.

Composition of the complexes : The composition of the complexes in solution were determined by Job's method¹⁷ with equimolar solution (4.69 × 10⁻⁴ M) of reagents I and II and Pd²⁺. The composition was further verified by mole-ratio¹⁸ method using a constant metal ion concentration (1 ml of 1.87 × 10⁻³ M solution). The composition of the complexes was found to be 1 : 2 with respect to metal : ligand.

Effect of diverse ions : The effect of foreign ions on the determination of Pd²⁺ with the reagents was studied by adding several foreign ions separately at different concentrations and measuring the absorbance of the complexes following the recommended procedure. It was observed that 200 ppm of Cd²⁺, Zn²⁺, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Al³⁺, Pt²⁺ and 400 ppm of citrate, tartrate, oxalate, nitrate, fluoride, sulphate, phosphate, EDTA and thiocyanate had no adverse effect on the determination of 4 ppm of Pd²⁺. However, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, WO₄²⁻, MoO₄²⁻, VO₃⁻, Ru³⁺, Ir³⁺, Rh³⁺, OSO₄²⁻ seriously interfere.

Degree of dissociation and stepwise formation constants : The degree of dissociation, α, and the dissociation constant, k, were calculated from the equation of Harvey and Manning. The dissociation constants were found to be 2.64 × 10⁻¹¹ and 25.33 × 10⁻¹⁰, respectively. So the overall stability constants are 3.79 × 10¹⁰ and 3.95 × 10⁸.

The log k₁ and log k₂ were evaluated by considering the degree of complex formation function (ϕ) and graphical extrapolation method of Leden. The stepwise formation constants were further verified by Yatsimirskii's method. The results are summarized in Table 1.

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Microgram Determination of Some Antipy- rines with N-bromosuccinimide.

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ANTIPYRINE and its derivatives, amidopyrine, analgin, novalgin and dolazine are important organic compounds widely used as pain relieving drugs. Several photometric methods using potassium ferricyanide¹, sodium nitrite², *p*-dimethyl amino benzaldehyde³, bromothymol blue⁴ and potassium aurichloride⁵ reagents have been reported for their determination.

We describe here the reaction of N-bromo-succinimide (NBS) with antipyrine and its derivatives in acetic acid medium. The colour of the reaction mixture has been utilized to develop a spectrophotometric method for the determination of the compounds in microgram amounts within $\pm 2\%$ error.

Experimental

Reagents : NBS solution (0.02 M) was prepared⁶ and standardised iodometrically⁶. Stock solutions of the samples were prepared by dissolving accurately weighed amounts of antipyrine, amidopyrine, analgin, novalgin, dolazine in distilled water in 100 ml volumetric flasks. Different aliquots of the solutions were used to have concentration range of 40-900 μg . The glacial acetic acid was B.D.H. A.R. quality.

Apparatus : Beckman model DU spectrophotometer equipped with a photomultiplier tube was

used for absorption measurements. Measurements at wavelength 290 nm were done using Beckman 1.005 cm silica cells.

Procedure : 5 ml aliquots from the stock solutions were taken in 25 ml volumetric flask to which 5 ml glacial acetic acid and 5 ml NBS (0.02 M) solution were added. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 15 min and made up to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance of the solution was measured against a reagent blank in the region of 250-450 nm (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Spectrum of (A) N-Bromosuccinimide, (B) Antipyrine, (C) Amidopyrine, (D) Analgin, (E) Novalgin, (F) Dolazine

Fig. 2. Spectrum of N-Bromosuccinimide and (A) Antipyrine, (B) Amidopyrine, (C) Analgin, (D) Novalgin, (E) Dolazine in acetic acid medium.

Calibration curves were prepared and it was found that the absorbtion follows a linear relationship to concentration. The amount of the drug in unknown samples was determined by measuring its absorbance at 290 nm and referring the data to the calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

The spectra of antipyrine, amidopyrine, analgin, novalgin, dolazine and NBS are recorded in Fig. 1. Antipyrine and its derivatives produce a stable yellow colour with NBS in acetic acid medium.